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The Love Song of J. Alfred Prufrock - A Critical Note

Rakesh Patel*

It has been a unique experience to have an acquaintance of an unusual account of love story of a modern man. Instead of projecting stereotype image of nature, man and his entanglements with the world, Eliot has created an artistic yellow picture of the modern affairs. *The Norton Anthology of English Literature* calls Prufrock's wish an allusion to Hamlet, the motion of the crab that suggests "futility and growing old" (1469).

Eliot does not take us to the faraway or imaginative world of romance here. He projects the sordid and pale side of human life very wonderfully instead. He makes use of "yellow" color repeatedly with a special purpose and Prufrock has sickening effect of this yellow color making his vision of perception faint and pale, and as a result the pale world appears before him. Even the evening appears him to be spreading out against the sky "like a patient etherized upon a table". The evening time is often considered to be romantic to have good time with one's love-mate but Prufrock sees the evening unromantic like an etherized passive patient and insist on his girlfriend to go with him in such atmosphere!! "The yellow fog" is compared to an animal rubbing its back upon the window-panes.

Eliot has created a distinct picture of a modern man in Prufrock. He has engaged with all sorts of works and there is a constant reference to tea-coffee, the marmalade and time. The plenty of time he has for "visions and revisions" before taking a toast and tea is sort of irony and satire on a modern man who has the absence of vision and reflection. His canvas of life is measured in terms of tea-coffee, toast and breakfast! The phrase "do I dare?" gets repeated in order to show the inaction or indecisiveness of a modern man.

The time brings change and that is how its effect is felt on Prufrock where he mentions that there is "a bald spot in the middle of my hair" is funny. He is conscious about his looks and knows that the people would gossip about it when he is old.

Prufrock has "known the evenings, mornings, afternoons" and there is a beautiful sarcastic expression comes on the surface when he says, "I have measured out my life with coffee spoons"! Nothing seems to be more significant in his life than tea-coffee-spoons and breakfast. He spends his days and ways recklessly as if he spits out "the butt-ends". And now, his life does not hold important events and accounts to cherish and has no vigor to perform any task. He is little bit confused with the

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idea how to presume.

Having mentioned to have knowledge of the ways of the world, Prufrock turns to share his familiarity with women by saying that he has “known the arms...arms that are braceleted and white and bare”. He has known them in their nakedness and still he feels the perfume from a dress that makes him digress from his task. Now he takes us to the dusky narrow streets and shows the smoke that rises from the pipes. The picture he shows us is of sordid and lonely city where nothing is seen except dusk and smoke!! He talks about his state of being absurd as if his energy has been consumed by the smoky sordid city. He thinks to have some sort of recreation by having tea-coffee and cakes in order to get back his strength “to force the moment to its crisis”. But the irony is that he does not have clutch over the moments and is succumbed to them completely. He realizes his grey age by referring to his head that has grown slightly bald which renders him into weak and powerless entity to suffer endlessly. Like John the Baptist, he has gone under the pangs of life and suffering but Prufrock, here, is not a prophet and witnesses his greatness flickering. Under such torturing experience he is afraid and being afraid and self-conscious is one of the characteristic of a modern man. Perhaps he has something worthwhile to share but weakness surrounds him and makes him inactive being. He compares himself with Lazarus, a biblical allusion, who has come down from the dead to share the unique experience he had there. But Prufrock fails to establish communication as if he is tongue-tied! Nobody understands him, not even his girlfriend. He talks about the fashionable world that gets depicted in novels and any other places but he feels to be cutoff from such fashionable life is estranged from the society. And now he regrets, “It is impossible to say just what I want”. Communication gap comes on the surface.

At some moments, he rejects the idea of being Hamlet in inaction. He prefers to be called himself an attendant lord instead, being the part of the process. He is caught up in a dilemma, like Rosencrantz and Guildenstern, where nobody understands him. He goes on regretting of his growing old age and thinks about his peculiar dressing style where he will have the bottoms of his trousers rolled. The problem of teeth also arises where he asks himself, “Do I dare to eat a peach?”

The idea of grey age overpowered Prufrock completely and he often slips into the past and says, “I have heard the mermaids singing” sounds unbelievable. Perhaps he might have the sixth sense but he denounces his extraordinary quality by remarking, “I do not think that they will sing to me”. He absorbs into a kind of fantasy where he mentions that he has lingered (with the mermaids) in the chambers of the sea. In a way, he seems to be going away from the reality and before the human voices wake him up, he wants have a deep sleep by drowning into the sea but it does not happen as there's no escape from the society!

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